

A Study of Recent Discovery of Buddhist Culture

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Abstract

This article will focus on a detailed analysis and observation on recent excavation in Danton, Midnapore and findings of Buddhist deities therein which speak for the dissemination of Buddhist culture there. Coming down from the Kalinga era, these findings denote clearly the relationship of Buddhism with ancient India. The name Danton comes down, as believed to a large extent, from 'Dantapur' which in its turn got the name for the preservation and celebration of the tooth of the Buddha as 'tooth' means 'donto' in vernacular language. The place has also opened up the existence of a Buddhist vihara or monastery which is probably the largest of its kind in West Bengal. It has the structure that resembles the viharas of Nalanda, Bikramsila, Paharpur and Mayanavati. This paper also emphasises on the joyful discovery of nearly ninety five bronze statues that reveals its enriched cultural heritage. During the excavation one surprising fact comes out regarding the location of the village where the excavation took place, and it informs that the entire village is situated on the ancient places and culture. So wide was the spread of Buddhism. This study also includes the existence of several Buddhist deities that speak for the arrival and nourishment of Mahayana Buddhism- Avalakitteswara, Bairachan, Tara, Saraswati, Hariti. These findings take note of the confluence of Hinayana and Mahayana Buddhism on the one hand and a deviation from Mahayana Buddhism to tread on a new track called Vajrayana Buddhism. The intention of this paper is to serve the historical and exegetical interpretation of Danton where instances of Buddhism abound.

Key Words: History, Buddhism, Deities, Mahayana, Vajrayana.

Moghalmari, also known as Mogolmari, is a hamlet and an archaeological excavation site located in the Dantan II CD block within the Kharagpur subdivision of the Paschim Medinipur district in West Bengal. Moghalmari is situated on the western bank of the Subarnarekha River in the West Medinipur district, approximately 3.2 miles north of Dantan. Since the beginning of the 21st century, a thorough excavation has uncovered the remnants of an old Buddhist Monastery.

Thus far is lost the history of Mogalmari which, to some historians, is also known as Amaravati. Vikramkesari was the ruler of this land whose daughter Sakhisena used to study there. Sakhisena was reported to have an affair with Ahimanik the facts of which had also been supported by the folklore penned in Fakir Ram's "Sakhisona". Famous Bengali writer Subodh Ghosh narrated this story as 'Sakhisenar Pathshala' (The School of Sakhisena) in his book "Kingbodontir Deshe" (In the Land of the Legends). All that remains of that history is just the shadow of its glory.

Moghalmari, a non-descript village on the south-west border of West Medinipur and West Bengal, has been recently brought to light as a vast archaeological site of early medieval Buddhist settlement having a gigantic Buddhist monastery, most likely of a pre-Pala era by the Department of Archaeology, Calcutta University, under the supervision of Dr. Asok Datta. However, the archaeological importance of the area of Dantan, which became a forgotten remnant of a (Danda) 'bhukti' and 'mandala' from the early medieval period, was earlier understood by the British historians and by Nagendranath Basu. One such British surveyor H. L. Harrison reported in 1873: "On the occasion of excavating earth to get out bricks and stones for the use of Rajghat Road under construction several magnificent remains of the old buildings have been discovered at Satdeula and Moghalmari, and bricks and stones, it is estimated have been dug out, numbering about 26 lakhs, and some crores yet lie buried under the ground."

Mogalmari is a village in the West Bengal – Odisha border that recently drew a lot of attention for the continuous findings that dates back to similar monasteries comparable to the likes of Vikramshila, Nalanda, Paharpur, Mainamati, etc. These were the hub of Buddhist settlement in India and continued to remain so even around 9th/ 10th CE.

Today, lying at one end of the village, the sprawling site is a testimony to a flourishing Buddhist enclave dating back to 6th to 7th century (post Gupta period/pre Pala period). Excavations so far have unearthed a Buddhist monastery, several stupa, bronze idols of Buddha, Bodhisattva and a Buddhist goddess, decorated stucco plastered wall and images, terracotta tablets, seals bearing post-Gupta Brahmi scripts, mixed metal coin bearing the name of King Samachardeva, gold pendant and part of the crown, etc. After deciphering some of the seals, experts said that the monastery was called the Sribandaka Vihara Aryabhikkhu Sangha. According to the late Prof. Datta, the monastery likely continued until the 12th century.

Needless to say that the name Mogalmari gives birth to a volley of debates. Some believe that the name came from a series of deaths of Mughal armies in Mughal-Pathan warfare. Some tend to convey a linguistic analysis of this name claiming that the word ‘mar’ means track or road. As Mughals used to tread this road, the name had been originated to mean the road walked upon by the Mughals.

Archaeology proves that this place contains a variety of historical documents which support the existence of largest Buddhist monastery in West Bengal.

In 1999, Dr. Ashok Dutta, professor of the Department of Archaeology, Calcutta University, came to Danton in West Midnapore to study the trade track by the side of the river Subarnarekha. There he met Sri Narendranath Biswas, retired Head Master of Danton High School. Mr. Biswas gave the information of Mogalmari to Dr. Dutta. In this village there is a mound named after Sakhisena which is situated in South-East corner of the village and under supervision of local club and library.

But the survey reveals that not only the mound but the entire village is located on the archaeological field. In due course the discovery of the relics of three rounded heap of bricks found in front of the house of Sri Kalipada Misra and a dedicated plaque inscribed with “E dharma hetu prabhava” (caused by this religion) in mixed Sanskrit-Prakrit language of 6th century AD ignited the interest of Dr. Dutta to unearth the mound.

The excavation unearthed a huge complex with massive walls, which date back to the 6th – 7th century CE. The excavation also suggests that the structure was built over two phases with the later one being built over the previous structure. The structure consisted of decorative bricks along with stucco work. The southern wall with richly decorated with a combination of decorative bricks and stucco works. The stucco includes floral motifs mostly predominated by lotus and lotus petals. Human figures occupied the shallow niches of the decorative south wall. The excavation continues today with restoration work being carried out on the exposed structure.

First phase (2003-2004):

In the North-West corner and the Southern part of the mound a square ditch was dug up having a shape of 6meter x 6meter. Entire mound was dissected into several ditches and named accordingly. At the North-West side, a square altar was found with a guard of three walls. The outer surface of those walls was decorated with a design made by bricks. Surveyors believe that the place earlier had been treated as a temple. In the southern part of the mound revealed four small cubicles having areas of 3.20 meter, 2.80 meter, 2.35 meter and 1.45 meter. These places were treated as the residence of Buddhist Bhikkhus.

Apart from that, another survey in the village brings out three rounded Buddhist stupas having the circumference of 2.80 meter, 2.00 meter and 1.25 meter. Smaller ones were connected with a track made of bricks. Also a pot made of soil was found in that survey which is red on the outer side and black on the inner side.

Second phase (2006-2007):

In this phase almost 20 ditches have been dug up in the East and West sides. In the east decorated walls, stucco walls, places for Bhikkhus to live in have been discovered. Survey down to .96 meter reveals a distorted statue of Buddha of 24 cmx14cm., burnt objects from Middle ages, iron and stoneware seal inscribed in siddhamatrika script of 6th century AD.

Third phase (2007-2008):

In this phase almost 12 ditches have been dug up in Northern, Eastern and central parts. A 58 meter long wall with a decorated gallstone has been discovered there. A wide path of bricks outside the wall has also been discovered. Within the wall residence of Bhikkhus, Buddhist stupas made of bricks, stucco, statue of stone, copper coins, design of stucco and lot of pots have been unearthed.

Fourth phase (2009-2010):

14 ditches have been dug up in the Northern side of the mound. The main entrance of the Buddhist vihara had been discovered. On both sides of the gate cubicles of same size had been found. This discovery is an important part of this excavation.

Fifth phase (2010-2011):

Here the excavation was done in the middle and the right parts of the mound. On the right side a boundary wall with stucco and gallstone of lime was found. Designs of lotus and Bodhi tree (Bo-tree) made of stucco admit the presence of vihara there. A track encompassing this boundary wall had been discovered which was used by Bhikkhus while paying homage to Buddha, Dhamma, Sangha. In this path a base of a rounded stupa had been found which might have been worshipped by laity. Stoneware seal with a perimeter of 3.5 cm had been discovered. Besides a dedicated plaque with a statue of meditating Buddha along with Bodhisattas on both sides was taken out. Some seals were inscribed with stupas, statues and words of Buddha.

Sixth phase (2011-2012):

This phase of excavation has been carried in two levels, and this was the last one under the leadership of Dr. Dutta. This excavation was done in the Southern and South-Western sides. In this phase the discovered vihara comprised 3600 square meter. The interesting discovery of this phase was the excavation of 13 statues of stucco stuck on the west facing wall. Analysing the artistic decorum Dr. Dutta opined that this vihara belonged to 6th century. Noteworthy of these statues are those of Kuber, Janguli, Avalokiteshwara, Lokeshwara, Gandharva, dancing men and women and many more. Apart from that the wall was ornamented with impression of lotus made of stucco, Dharmachakka and several geometrical designs.

In the second level excavation led to the discovery of stoneware seals comprising words of the Buddha, lantern of stoneware, attar pots, designed bricks, pots and so on. Dr. Dutta then concluded that vihara of this second phase was built on the ruined vihara that was discovered in the first phase. The monastery of the second phase or level was supposedly built from 9th to 10th century. The vihara of the first level was set up in 6th century.

Based on the instances of this excavation conducted by the Department of Archaeology, Calcutta University and the report of State Archaeological Museum, Information and Cultural Affairs of the Govt. of West Bengal has declared 'Sakhisena dhibi' a heritage site. The seventh phase of excavation has been initiated by the heartfelt effort of Sri Amal Roy, Deputy Director of State Archaeological Museum since 24th November, 2013.

Seventh phase (2013-2014):

36 ditches had been dug up on the western, northern and south-western sides of the mound. A task of preservation also went side by side with excavation. In the west of the mound a boundary wall, sacred place, track, residence of Bhikkhus had been revealed. That the monastery had been built in several stages was attested by the excavation deep down to 8 meter just outside the boundary

wall. In the field 4 stucco statues were unearthed besides 13 stucco statues of which the statue of Manjushree was important. Moreover 10 differently designed bricks had also been discovered. Excavation on the entrance in the northern side brought out the existence of staircase to go down to the vihara, flagstaff, water sewage system. From the residence of the Bhikkhus the torso of the statue of the Buddha with an inscription in Brahmi script of 6th century AD had been revealed. Apart from that several golden lockets and dedicated plaque of terracotta from 6th century had been discovered. The important discovery of this phase of excavation is the name plate of the vihara found in the same ditch that gave lockets. Surveyors and researchers primarily opined that the name plate consisted the words “Sribandak Mahavihare Aryabhikkhu Sangha” that leads to further expectation of several viharas. They also opine that this is a ‘mahavihara’ or grand monastery. They have also been trying to decode some seals found therein during excavation.

The otherwise non-descript village during the last half of January 2016 saw a lot of excitement as around 40 bronze artefacts, dating back to fifth and sixth centuries, tumbled out of the earth, as the state archaeology department re-launched the excavation of the Buddhist monastery after a gap of two years. As a bronze Buddha statuette, measuring 7cm X 6cm, first surfaced in the middle trench of the site, several more statues of varying sizes started showing up. Monks from across the country, who have converged on Moghalmari for special prayers and seminars at a festival that coincided with the excavation believes that these place could be a site of early Buddhist settlement in India.

Apart from structural finding the excavation also unearthed several statues of Buddha, Bodhisattva and a Buddhist gods and goddess, including a few bronze statues. The finding also included terracotta tablets, seals bearing post-Gupta Brahmi scripts, mixed metal coin bearing the name of King Samachardeva, gold pendant and part of the crown, etc. The deciphering the inscription on the seals it was confirmed that Moghalmari actually consists of two monasteries. The two

monasteries were Mugalayikaviharika and Yajñapindikamahavihara. Presence of two same period monasteries in the same compound are unique in eastern India.

It is really a joyful fact that the history so long earthed for 1500 years has been read out by Dr. Ashok Dutta. Tourists and researchers find this monastery as a specimen to study history. This discovery adds a new chapter to the pages of history and history of Buddhism gets enriched with the inclusion of this episode. We are hopeful that successful completion of this process of excavation will lead Mogalmari to place itself in world history.

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